

APICURON, A Platform for Crediting & Recognizing Research Assets

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Abstract.

APICURON is a platform that credits and recognizes scientific contributions, especially non-traditional research outputs such as curated data, training materials, research software, and workflows. By integrating with research repositories and databases, it tracks contributor activities, supports contributors' engagement, and enables recognition through platforms like ORCID. APICURON empowers both institutions and researchers, promoting a broader view of scientific impact and crediting work beyond traditional academic metrics.

Conference Themes: Recognition of Contributions to Open Science

Keywords: Credit, Recognition, Open Science, Scientific Data, Scientific Infrastructure

1. General Platform Description

APICURON is a dedicated platform for acknowledging and crediting scientific contributions, particularly non-traditional research assets. It directly addresses the challenge of attributing and quantifying the significant effort involved in collecting, curating, and processing scientific data, an endeavor often overlooked by traditional academic metrics. By providing a standardized and verifiable mechanism for recognition, APICURON aims to promote a more holistic and inclusive view of research impact.

2. The Target Audiences

In its mission to provide comprehensive credit and recognition, APICURON serves two primary entities: research publishing platforms (e.g., research asset repositories and biological databases) responsible for curating and disseminating research, and the individual scientists who contribute their work to these platforms.

For publishing platforms, APICURON offers the ability to evaluate contributors' engagement in an open science context. This works through an integration process where platforms can start by:

1. Defining a recognition Model on APICURON: This model specifies which research activities are recognized and configures associated reward mechanisms (e.g., badges, medals) based on the defined research activities.
2. Submitting contribution data mapped to the previously defined research activities, attaching a reference to the contributor, the type of contribution, and the time at which it occurred, as represented below (fig 1)

Fig 1: APICURON - Basic Activity Object

This integration offers a structured baseline that allows APICURON to aggregate data to various reward mechanisms that are customizable and adaptable to differing use cases. APICURON serves this aggregated information to the platform, offering feedback based on the recognition model. By closing this feedback loop, research publishing platforms benefit from a broad view of their research community (measuring engagement, interests, etc) and can adapt the recognition model accordingly or enhance features to cater to their community's evolving needs, all while continuously iterating on this process. This fosters a more dynamic and inclusive ecosystem for research asset development and recognition.

For scientists and contributors, APICURON offers a powerful avenue to showcase scientific work that results in non-traditional research outputs, which are frequently overlooked through conventional research evaluation systems focused on traditional publications. It provides a direct and verifiable endorsement from the contributing platforms, significantly enhancing a scientist's CV.

APICURON has an active integration with ORCID, a researcher PID (Persistent Identifier) provider that offers the ability for researchers to publish and share their CVs.

Through this integration, APICURON automatically submits a customizable summary of a researcher's contributions to their ORCID profile (fig 2 [1]). This summary can be adjusted for granularity, includes links back to the researcher's APICURON profile for more details, and is updated according to the recognition model defined by the research publishing platform.

Fig 2: APICURON contribution pipeline and propagation

This structured and verifiable approach to crediting can, over time, contribute to the emergence of more standardized metrics for evaluating the impact and quality of non-traditional research assets across the scientific community.

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